

Supplementary Information

Ambipolar Blend-based Organic Electrochemical Transistors and Inverters

*Eyal Stein¹, Oded Nahor¹, Mikhail Stolov², Viatcheslav Freger², Iuliana Maria Petruta³, Iain McCulloch^{3,4}
and Gitti L. Frey^{1,*}.*

Supplementary Table 1 | Summary of OECT characteristics for pristine materials and other blend compositions

Material	Polarity	$g_{m,max}[S\text{ cm}^{-1}]^a$	$\mu C^*[F\text{ cm}^{-1}V^{-1}S^{-1}]^b$	$V_{th}[V]^c$
Pristine				
PrC ₆₀ MA	n	6.1 ± 0.5	21.7 ± 1.6	0.620 ± 0.005
p(g2T-TT)	p	97.6 ± 5.2	324.3 ± 17.7	0.001 ± 0.003
90:10				
PrC ₆₀ MA	n	2.5 ± 0.5	8.8 ± 1.4	0.617 ± 0.009
p(g2T-TT)	p	11.4 ± 1.4	45.8 ± 7.2	-0.049 ± 0.014
99:1				
PrC ₆₀ MA	n	2.6 ± 0.4	10.3 ± 1.4	0.645 ± 0.014
p(g2T-TT)	p	0.012 ± 0.014	0.023 ± 0.018	- ^d

a) Calculated from transfer curves according to $g_m = \frac{\partial I_D}{\partial V_G}$ divided by $\frac{Wd}{L}$

b) Calculated with $W = 1000\mu\text{m}$, $L = 30\mu\text{m}$, $d = 60\text{nm}$ according to $g_{m,max} = \frac{Wd}{L} \mu C^* |V_{th} - V_G|$

c) Calculated with linear fit of $\sqrt{I_D}$ vs V_G at $V_D = \pm 0.4\text{V}$

d) Cannot be extracted reliably from the results

Supplementary Figure 1 | OECT characteristics of pristine materials. (a), (b) Output and (c), (d) Transfer characteristics of pristine p(g2T-TT) and PrC₆₀MA, respectively.

Supplementary Figure 2 | Reproducibility of OECT characteristics of the 95:5 blend. Displayed are (a) output and (b) transfer characteristics of 8 different devices.

Supplementary Table 2 | The transient response time of an ambipolar 95:5 blend OECT extracted from the data resented in Supplementary Figure 3

	<i>Sampling 1</i>	<i>Sampling 2</i>	<i>Sampling 3</i>	<i>Average</i>
<i>n</i> – type				
τ_{ON} [ms]	22.7 ± 0.4	19.9 ± 0.5	17.8 ± 0.4	20 ± 3
τ_{OFF} [ms]	5.56 ± 0.06	5.58 ± 0.07	5.37 ± 0.08	5.6 ± 0.1
<i>p</i> – type				
τ_{ON} [ms]	502 ± 19	401 ± 17	494 ± 23	466 ± 56
τ_{OFF} [ms]	5.6 ± 0.1	6.3 ± 0.1	5.5 ± 0.1	5.8 ± 0.4

Supplementary Figure 3 | Transient response time analysis of the ambipolar 95:5 blend OECT, with exponential fit curves.

Supplementary Figure 4 | Spectroelectrochemical properties of materials and blend. (a) Rule-of-mixtures calculated and (b) measured absorption spectra for 95:5 w:w PrC₆₀MA:p(g2T-TT) blend. (c) Absorption and (d) absorption changes in pristine p(g2T-TT). (e) Absorption and (f) absorption changes in pristine PrC₆₀MA. The potentials applied are $-0.9V < V_{WE} < +0.3V$ vs Ag/AgCl pellet. Absorption changes are with respect to the recorded $V_{WE} = -0.4V$ curve.

Supplementary Figure 5 | Vibronic absorption peaks. Absorption in the $\pi - \pi^*$ peaks of p(g2T-TT) at $-0.4V$ applied between the film-coated FTO WE and an Ag/AgCl pellet RE with a Pt wire as CE. A notable red-shift is observed in the 0-0 and 0-1 peaks, as well as an increase in the A_{0-0}/A_{0-1} ratio.

Supplementary Figure 6 | Energy band diagram and Electrochemical window. The energy levels of p(g2T-TT)¹ and PrC₆₀MA², work function of Au electrodes and the corresponding water electrochemical window at pH=7 vs Vacuum level and vs Ag/AgCl reference electrode³. The HOMO of p(g2T-TT) and the LUMO of PrC₆₀MA are symmetric about ~-4.25eV, which corresponds to a voltage of +0.35V vs Ag/AgCl.

Supplementary Figure 7 | EQCM of pristine materials. Mass changes in EQCM measurement of p(g2T-TT) (blue curve) and PrC₆₀MA (red curve), as calculated from the Sauerbrey equation for the 3rd overtone. Voltage applied between the gold-coated quartz sensor and an Ag/AgCl (3M KCl) reference electrode with a Pt wire CE. Scan rate was 10mV/sec.

Supplementary Figure 8 | EQCM of 75:25 blend. Mass changes in EQCM measurement of a 75:25 w:w PrC₆₀MA:p(g2T-TT) blend, as calculated from the Sauerbrey equation for the 3rd overtone. Region marked in red are mass gain in the PrC₆₀MA phase, blue regions are mass gain in the p(g2T-TT) phase. Voltage applied between the gold-coated quartz sensor and an Ag/AgCl (3M KCl) reference electrode with a Pt wire CE. Scan rate was 10mV/sec.

Supplementary Figure 9 | Grazing Incidence Wide-Angle Scattering (GIWAXS) of pristine PrC₆₀MA annealed at 120°C for 20min.

Supplementary Figure 10 | X-Ray Diffraction Peak Analysis of pristine materials and 95:5 blend. (a) Peak identification for the extraction of lamellar stacking d-space. (b) and (c) Peak FWHM fitting using Pseudo-Voigt function for peak orders 3-8 for the extraction of coherence length⁴ for pristine PrC₆₀MA and PrC₆₀MA in the blend, respectively. First-order peaks and peaks that diverge significantly from the general trend are disregarded in the linear fitting

Supplementary References

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